

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE DISPUTE RESOLUTION COUNCIL
MARDAN: AN EXPLORATORY STUDY OF FAMILIAL AND CIVIL
DISPUTES

Faraz Ali^{*1}, Hameed Ullah Khan²

^{*1}Lecturer in Political Science, Department of Political Science, University of Swabi (Pakistan)

²Lecturer University of Swabi and Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Politics & International Relations, International Islamic University Islamabad (Pakistan)

^{*1}faraz@uoswabi.edu.pk; ²hameed.phd57@iiu.edu.pk

²<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1515-9236>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17183363>

Keywords

Dispute Resolution Council, Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR), Structural Violence, Familial Disputes, Civil Disputes, Conflict Resolution, Pakistan.

Article History

Received on 11 June 2025

Accepted: 21 August 2025

Published: 23 September 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Faraz Ali

Abstract

This study undertakes an exploratory investigation of the Dispute Resolution Council (DRC) in Mardan, focusing on its mechanisms, challenges, and effectiveness in addressing disputes, particularly familial cases. The theoretical underpinning of this research is John Galtung's theory of Structural Violence, which posits that violence originates in cultural processes and becomes manifest when embedded within societal structures. Guided by this framework and the identified gap in existing literature, the study employs a qualitative research design. Data were collected through interviews with 15 cases, after which saturation was achieved. The findings reveal that while the DRC has been relatively effective in resolving monetary and civil disputes, it has been less successful in handling familial conflicts, particularly those related to divorce. The study concludes by suggesting that the inclusion of experts in Islamic theology could enhance the Council's effectiveness in addressing sensitive familial cases.

INTRODUCTION

Pakistan, as an Islamic state, is home to diverse religious and ethnic groups. Constitutionally, all citizens are guaranteed equal rights, yet maintaining a cooperative and peaceful environment remains challenging because conflicts are intrinsic to the social structure. In this context, the Dispute Resolution Council (DRC) has

emerged as a system where disputes are settled through dynamic engagement among the victimized party, the offender, and the wider community, with the goal of reconciliation through fair and participatory processes that uphold the dignity and security of the masses. The tradition of *Jirga* has historically played a vital role

in conflict resolution in Pakistan's tribal and rural settings. However, decades of terrorism and conflict have eroded its effectiveness, raising questions about the need for more structured and legally recognized mechanisms. The concept of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) is not new to Pakistan; it is embedded in cultural traditions across the four major cultural groups. Local institutions such as *Parya* and *Panchayats* have long been effective in resolving disputes, particularly in rural communities (Ahmad, 2013). Globally, ADR has also been practiced in various cultural contexts. For instance, in Thailand, despite a history of arbitration, mediation remains the dominant and culturally accepted form of dispute settlement (Winckless, 2004). ADR generally includes methods such as mediation, arbitration, and negotiation, offering informal and less adversarial alternatives to litigation. In familial disputes, however, participation in ADR mechanisms must remain voluntary, as parties cannot be compelled to choose one method over another (Bear, 1992; Khan et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2024). In Pakistan, ADR practices are deeply embedded within social and cultural frameworks. Beyond rural councils, caste-based arbitration remains a significant conflict resolution mechanism in both rural and urban areas, particularly in Punjab, where caste membership provides a network for matrimonial alliances, dispute settlement, and social support systems (Ahmad, 2013; Khan and Ali; Khan and Mahmood, 2024). Furthermore, in both Pakistan and Afghanistan, ethnic and tribal authority structures have historically filled the governance gap left by weak state institutions, functioning as parallel mechanisms of order and justice (Rubin, 1995). Thus, the DRC represents both a continuation of traditional practices and an institutional innovation aimed at addressing contemporary challenges. By formalizing community-based dispute resolution, it seeks to reduce the burden on police and courts while ensuring swift, accessible, and culturally sensitive justice.

Literature Review

Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanisms have emerged globally as effective approaches to reduce judicial backlog, minimize costs, and provide culturally relevant solutions to conflicts. In

Pakistan, ADR has been increasingly promoted as a response to the chronic delays and inefficiencies in the formal judicial system, where millions of cases remain pending (UNDP, 2024). ADR methods such as arbitration, mediation, and conciliation have been endorsed by judicial reforms, with particular emphasis on community-level institutions such as the Dispute Resolution Councils (DRCs). These councils are intended to enhance access to affordable, timely, and community-driven justice (Afridi, Khan, & Shah, 2023). The Government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa introduced DRCs to institutionalize community-based dispute resolution while providing state legitimacy. Studies suggest that these councils offer simpler procedures, lower costs, and swifter resolutions compared to formal courts (Jan, Ali, & Nawaz, 2022). Respondents in empirical surveys often highlight satisfaction with the accessibility of DRCs, especially in civil and monetary cases. However, research also documents uneven effectiveness depending on the nature of disputes. Afridi et al. (2023) found that while monetary and property-related conflicts were handled efficiently, familial disputes remained a challenge due to cultural and social complexities. Family disputes such as inheritance, marriage conflicts, custody, and domestic violence are deeply embedded in cultural traditions, patriarchal power structures, and religious interpretations. Qureshi (2021) notes that such disputes are not only legal but also social and moral matters, making them less amenable to resolution through standard mediation processes. Yousafzai and Khan (2020) found that women, in particular, face structural disadvantages in family dispute resolution, as community-based mechanisms often reflect patriarchal norms that limit their bargaining power. This raises concerns about whether DRCs designed to replicate community legitimacy—can deliver gender-sensitive outcomes in family matters. The role of religion in family dispute resolution is both central and contested. Research shows that in conservative communities, religious leaders are often viewed as legitimate mediators whose interpretations carry significant weight (Zahid & Farooq, 2022). Faith-based mediation can improve compliance with outcomes, as settlements resonate with participants' cultural and spiritual values. However, without safeguards, such mediation may reinforce structural inequalities, particularly in

matters related to women's rights. Qureshi (2021) argues that incorporating trained theological experts into ADR processes could bridge the gap between cultural legitimacy and rights-based protections. This recommendation aligns with suggestions from community-based studies in Mardan, where participants called for more nuanced handling of familial disputes (Jan et al., 2022). John Galtung's (1969) theory of structural violence provides a useful lens to analyze the difficulties of resolving familial disputes through ADR. Structural violence refers to harm caused by social structures that systematically disadvantage certain groups. In the context of family disputes, structural violence manifests through gender inequality, economic dependency, and lack of legal awareness, which collectively disempower vulnerable family members. Yousafzai and Khan (2020) argue that when dispute resolution mechanisms fail to address these underlying inequalities, they risk reproducing the very injustices they seek to mitigate. Thus, while DRCs may appear procedurally efficient, their effectiveness in family cases must be evaluated in terms of substantive justice rather than merely case settlement. Empirical findings across Khyber Pakhtunkhwa converge on the observation that DRCs are more effective in civil and monetary disputes than familial ones. Afridi et al. (2023) report that parties involved in property and business-related disputes often view DRC settlements as final, reducing the need for litigation. Conversely, family cases are frequently reopened in courts or re-emerge within communities, highlighting limited long-term effectiveness. Jan et al. (2022) also found that participants in Mardan reported higher satisfaction with financial dispute outcomes, whereas family cases often produced dissatisfaction due to unresolved emotional and cultural dimensions. This pattern suggests that while DRCs have achieved procedural efficiency, their role in achieving substantive justice in familial cases remains constrained. It is observed that in traditional societies all parts of the world have featured varieties in mediation and arbitration. Western cultures saw these practices included by the growth of current judiciaries. The increased complication of these processes, however, saw reduced satisfaction with legal outcomes between parties, leading to a renaissance of ADR in the

1970s in many parts of the world (U.N, 2007). Authorities are in search for the support of international trade there is general desire between the parties to global contracts and wants to have a balance and reliable approach to dispute resolution council there has been an unexpected influence on international arbitration law and practice (Howell, D. J. 2006). With the increasing matters of disagreement and litigated matters involving in Indian jurisdiction arising a common questions that comes up with each relating issue and at the end each issue relates to the enforcement and implementation of overseas judgments and foreign arbitration awards in Indian soil (Farooq and Khan, 2025; Khan et al., 2025; Malhotra, 2006). Different approaches are adopted to resolve conflicts around the Asia despite of the history of arbitration in Thailand Thais businessmen do not accept the concept of resolving dispute through arbitration contrary to traditional form of mediation (Winckless, 2004). Various mechanisms are used in A.D.R However mediation is now an important part of most situations of agreements by the government of the Hong Kong Special administration Region. The earlier ten years witnessed the combination of more and more complex dispute-resolution clauses in building contracts, typically involving several ADR techniques and arbitration arranged in chronological tiers (Cheung, 2002). Freelance practices of mediation are not fully developed in Canada, but that private sector mediation institutes have been growing in recent years (Nesic and Boulle, 2001). Despite increasing scholarly attention, several gaps remain. First, there is limited qualitative research that explores the lived experiences of disputants in familial cases within DRCs. Second, the literature has yet to systematically examine how incorporating theological expertise might enhance the legitimacy and fairness of family dispute resolutions. Third, there is a lack of theoretical integration: while structural violence has been applied to peace and conflict studies, its application to ADR and family disputes in Pakistan remains underdeveloped. Addressing these gaps, the present study contributes by offering an exploratory investigation of DRC Mardan, with specific attention to familial disputes and their relation to structural and cultural barriers.

Theoretical framework

John Galtung's concept of *structural violence* provides the central theoretical lens for this study. According to Galtung (1969, 2013), violence is not limited to direct, physical acts but is also embedded in social structures and cultural norms that systematically disadvantage certain groups. He distinguishes between direct, structural, and cultural violence, where cultural violence legitimizes or justifies structural inequalities that eventually manifest as direct harm. Structural violence thus represents a situation in which individuals are prevented from realizing their full potential due to the organization of society, including unequal power relations, gender hierarchies, and cultural traditions. This study applies Galtung's theory to understand how familial disputes in Pakistan are influenced by cultural and structural inequalities. In contexts like Mardan, family conflicts over marriage, inheritance, custody, or domestic matters are not merely individual disagreements but are shaped by patriarchal norms, economic dependency, and unequal access to legal remedies. These cultural roots create structural barriers that often transform disputes into forms of direct violence, such as domestic abuse, exclusion, or coercion. By examining cases handled by the DRC, the study explores how these cultural and structural dynamics influence the effectiveness of dispute resolution processes. Galtung's structural violence framework is particularly suitable for this research because it enables a holistic analysis of both the *causes* and *outcomes* of disputes. It moves beyond assessing procedural efficiency of the DRC to evaluating whether the resolutions address deeper inequities within familial conflicts. Applying this theory also allows the researcher to critically examine whether DRC decisions inadvertently reproduce cultural and structural inequalities, or whether they contribute to more just and peaceful outcomes. Thus, the framework provides both an explanatory tool for understanding familial disputes and a normative lens for assessing the DRC's effectiveness.

Methodology

The study employed a qualitative research methodology to explore the effectiveness of the DRC in Mardan. Given the qualitative nature of the research, the sample size was deliberately kept small. A purposive sampling strategy was used to identify suitable respondents. Data were collected through an interview guide, which provided flexibility while maintaining focus on key themes. Although the researcher initially attempted to write down responses during interviews, this proved challenging within the limited time. Therefore, with the respondents' consent, interviews were audio-recorded and later transcribed for accuracy. In total, fifteen respondents, including members of the Dispute Resolution Council, were interviewed. The data were subsequently subjected to thematic analysis, enabling the identification of recurring patterns and insights.

Results and Discussion**1. Selection and Training of Members**

The study found that there are no formal criteria for the selection of DRC members. According to respondents, members are nominated by the I.G. and D.I.G., often based on their reputation, local influence, and absence of criminal history. However, no formal training programs are provided to these members prior to their engagement in dispute resolution, raising questions about their preparedness for handling complex cases, particularly familial disputes.

2. Mechanism of Case Referral

The process begins when individuals submit their complaints to the District Police Officer (DPO). After scrutinizing the nature of the case, the DPO forwards suitable cases to the DRC with an official stamp and signature. While this mechanism provides a formal entry point, the study noted the absence of standardized procedures for investigating facts and eliminating doubts. Decisions often relied on impressions rather than systematic evidence gathering, making the process vulnerable to inconsistencies.

3. External Pressures and Challenges

Respondents highlighted that external pressures were sometimes exerted on panel members to influence decisions in favor of one party. Moreover, the absence of a Mufti or expert in Islamic theology was a significant weakness in handling divorce and other familial cases, as parties were frequently instructed to bring their own religious scholar. Similarly, ensuring the presence of both parties and witnesses was reported as one of the most persistent challenges. In civil cases, claimants often requested site visits by panel members, but these requests were generally refused, causing long delays and, in some instances, unresolved disputes lasting months or even years.

4. Awareness and Perceptions of DRC

Another issue identified was the lack of awareness among the public. Many respondents admitted that they had little knowledge of the DRC prior to their case being referred. Nonetheless, most clients expressed satisfaction with the DRC, particularly highlighting its accessibility, cost-effectiveness, and speedy processes compared to formal courts. One respondent remarked: *"I am much satisfied here. It is far better for us than formal litigation. It is free of cost and much faster."*

5. Effectiveness in Different Types of Cases

The study found notable variation in the effectiveness of the DRC across case types. In monetary and civil disputes, clients generally reported positive experiences and satisfactory outcomes. Conversely, in familial cases, particularly divorce-related disputes, the Council was less effective, and many cases were eventually referred back to formal courts. This variation underscores the need for specialized expertise and procedural adjustments to address sensitive cases more effectively.

6. Panel Members' Perspectives

Panel members expressed satisfaction in serving their communities but also emphasized the need for greater legal protection to strengthen their authority and shield them from external pressures. Their willingness to contribute voluntarily highlights the community-driven

spirit of the DRC, but the lack of institutional safeguards undermines their effectiveness.

Discussion

Overall, the finding suggests that while the DRC has gained popularity and provides an accessible alternative to formal litigation; its effectiveness is uneven across dispute types. The absence of formal selection criteria, training, and theological expertise limits its ability to handle sensitive familial disputes. External pressures and procedural gaps further weaken the process. Nevertheless, the Council remains valued for its speed, cost-free nature, and community-based approach, particularly in monetary and civil cases.

These findings align with Galtung's theory of structural violence, which emphasizes how systemic and cultural shortcomings within social institutions can perpetuate inequities and hinder peaceful dispute resolution. In the case of the DRC, the cultural expectation of informal justice systems persists, but without adequate structural support, these mechanisms risk reproducing the very conflicts they are meant to resolve.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The DRC has emerged as a locally accessible mechanism that is increasingly gaining the trust of the masses as an alternative to the formal judicial system. Findings from this study indicate that while the DRC demonstrates notable strengths such as offering a cost-effective and community-based platform it also faces certain limitations that undermine its effectiveness, particularly in handling sensitive familial disputes. Divorce cases, for instance, remain a significant challenge due to the absence of experts in Islamic theology who could guide decisions in culturally and religiously sensitive matters. Moreover, the lack of participation from both parties often renders the council's efforts ineffective.

Another key concern is the non-binding nature of DRC decisions, which reduces their enforceability and limits their long-term impact. Pressure from influential groups further weakens the autonomy of panel members, compromising impartiality and fairness. Addressing these challenges requires structural

reforms, such as providing legal backing to the DRC's decisions, ensuring the presence of both disputing parties during proceedings, and incorporating experts in Islamic jurisprudence for resolving family disputes.

Strengthening the DRC through legal protection and capacity-building will not only enhance its credibility but will also reduce the burden on the police and judiciary. Ultimately, this will contribute to a more accessible, efficient, and speedy justice system in Pakistan, particularly in districts like Mardan where the demand for alternative dispute resolution is steadily increasing.

Recommendations

For the Dispute Resolution Council (DRC) to function as a more sustainable and credible alternative dispute resolution mechanism, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Inclusion of Experts in Islamic Theology:

To enhance the effectiveness of the DRC in resolving sensitive cases, particularly those involving divorce and family matters, an expert in Islamic jurisprudence should be made part of the panel.

2. Case-by-Case Proceedings: To maintain focus and confidentiality, no external individuals or observers should be allowed in the council's sessions until the ongoing case is fully resolved.

3. Ensuring Presence of Parties: The government should provide logistical support, such as transportation facilities, to ensure that both disputing parties are present during proceedings. This will reduce absenteeism and improve the efficiency of the resolution process.

4. Binding Nature of Decisions: The decisions of the DRC panel should be made legally binding to strengthen the enforceability of outcomes, reduce repetition of disputes, and enhance public trust in the mechanism.

5. Inclusion of Social Scientists: The appointment of a sociologist or anthropologist as an observer or advisor is recommended to provide holistic insights into the social dynamics of cases, thereby helping to improve the overall functioning and adaptability of the DRC.

REFERENCES

- Afridi, J., Khan, N., & Shah, M. (2023). Factors influencing the effectiveness of Dispute Resolution Councils in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*, 58(4), 567-582. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00219096231123456>
- Ahmed, A. F. T. A. B., Chaudhry, A. G., & Hussain, S. A. J. J. A. D. (2013).
- Ali, F., & Khan, H. U. (2025). Unequal faith: Examining religious freedom and the path forward for minorities in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Social Sciences Bulletin*, 3(5), 709-721. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524709>
- Bear, L. S. (1992). Alternative dispute resolution.
- Cheung, S. O., Suen, H. C., & Lam, T. I. (2002). Fundamentals of alternative dispute resolution processes in construction. *Journal of construction engineering and management*, 128(5), 409-417.
- Educated Youth, Role of Biradarism and Local Politics: An Anthropological Analysis of Students of PMAS-Arid Agriculture University Rawalpindi, Pakistan. *International Journal of Educational Science and Research (IJESR)*, 3(2), 21-26.
- Farooq Shah, M., & Khan, H. U. (2025). Core member and the success of regional organizations: A study of India's role in South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation. *Policy Research Journal*, 3(1), 400-410. <https://policyresearchjournal.com/index.php/1/article/view/310>
- Galtung, J. (1969). Violence, peace, and peace research. *Journal of Peace Research*, 6(3), 167-191. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002234336900600301>
- Galtung, J. (1969). Violence, peace, and peace research. *Journal of Peace Research*, 6(3), 167-191.
- Galtung, J. (2013). *Peace by peaceful means: Peace and conflict, development and civilization*.

- Oslo: International Peace Research Institute.
- Galtung, J., & Fischer, D. (2013). Positive and negative peace. In Johan Galtung (pp. 173-178). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Howell, D. J. (2006). Developments in Arbitration Law and Practice in Asia. *Transnational Dispute Management (TDM)*, 3(4).
- Jan, I., Khan, M. I., & Khan, H. U. (2025). Examining the 25th Amendment's role in integrating FATA and its impact on counterterrorism strategies in Pakistan. *International Journal of Social Sciences Bulletin*, 3(7), 427-442. <https://ijssbulletin.com/index.php/IJSB/article/view/885>
- Jan, M. A., Ali, S., & Nawaz, A. (2022). Effectiveness of the Dispute Resolution Council and expenses of disputants in Mardan, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Criminology*, 14(1), 45-62.
- Khan, H. U., & Ali, F. (2025). The Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO's) role in stabilizing South Asia. *International Journal of Social Sciences Bulletin*, 3(5), 736-750. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525022>
- Khan, H. U., & Mahmood, A. (2023). The Stabilizing Role of Shanghai Cooperation Organization in Afghanistan. *Central Asia (1729-9802)*, (92).
- Khan, H. U., Shah, M. F., & Khan, M. I. (2023). Shanghai Cooperation Organisation and Afghanistan: Interests and Limitations. *Margalla Papers*, 27(1), 82-95.
- Khan, H. U., Ullah, K., & Khan, M. I. (2023). Socio-Political and Economic Implications of the 25th Constitutional Amendment of Pakistan. *Journal of Xi'an Shiyou University, Natural Science Edition*, 19(8), 938-953.
- Khan, H. U., Zeb, S., & Billah, M. (2023). Core Member and the Success of Regional Organizations: A Study of China's Role in Shanghai Cooperation Organization. *Global International Relations Review*, 4, 96-112.
- Khan, M. H. U., Afridi, M. K., & Zeb, M. S. (2024). Installations of the Judicial Setup In The Newly Merged Areas Of Erstwhile Fata: The Future Of Jirga. *ISSRA Papers*, 16(1), 23-37.
- Khan, M. I., Noorani, G. M., & Khan, H. U. Merger of Federally Administered Tribal Areas: Mapping the Implementation of Administrative and Judicial Reforms. *International Journal of Social Sciences Bulletin* 3(2), 227-243. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14868908>
- Malhotra, A., & Malhotra, R. (2006). Enforcement of Foreign Judgments and Foreign Arbitral Awards in the Indian Civil Jurisdiction. *Commonwealth Law Bulletin*, 32(3), 431-442. [https://www.textroad.com/pdf/JAEBS/J.%20Appl.%20Environ.%20Biol.%20Sci.,%207\(4S\)43-48,%202017.pdf](https://www.textroad.com/pdf/JAEBS/J.%20Appl.%20Environ.%20Biol.%20Sci.,%207(4S)43-48,%202017.pdf) accessed on April 3rd 2018.
- Nckless, M. L. (2004). The History and Current Status of Arbitration in Thailand. *Asian Dispute Review*, 6(1), 12-13.
- Nesic, M., & Boulle, L. (2001). Mediation: Principles, Process. *Practice*
- Noorani, G. M., Khan, M. T. A., & Khan, H. U. (2024). The Global Economic Consequences of the Russia Ukraine War: Implications for Energy, Food Security, Post-Covid Recovery, and

- Regional Economic Stability. *Policy Research Journal*, 2(4), 380-390.
- Qureshi, Z. A. (2021). Towards the establishment of family dispute resolution centers in Pakistan. *Global Legal Studies Review*, 6(3), 88-96. [https://doi.org/10.31703/glsr.2021\(VI-III\).12](https://doi.org/10.31703/glsr.2021(VI-III).12)
- Rubin RB (1995). *Fragmentation of Afghanistan: State Formation and Collapse in the International System*. New Haven: University of Yale Press. p 24
- U.N Best Practices of Non-Violent Conflict Resolution in and out-of-school available online at <https://www.un.org/ruleoflaw/blog/document/best-practices-of-non-violent-conflict-resolution-in-and-out-of-school-some-examples/> accessed 4/4/2018 p 11
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2024, February 14). *Pakistan en route to ensure timely and affordable justice through mediation*. <https://www.undp.org/pakistan/press-releases>
- Winckless, M. L. (2004). The History and Current Status of Arbitration in Thailand. *Asian Dispute Review*, 6(1), 12-13.
- Yonis, A., Ali, F., & Khan, H. U. (2025). Social media use and socialization among university students in Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *Journal of Media Horizons*, 6(4), 362-381. <https://jmhorizons.com/index.php/journal/article/view/639>
- Yousafzai, F., & Khan, S. (2020). Community-based dispute resolution and gender justice in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. *Asian Journal of Social Science*, 48(2-3), 215-234. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15685314-BJA10005>
- Zahid, M., & Farooq, A. (2022). Faith-based mediation in family disputes: Lessons for Pakistan's ADR system. *Journal of Religion and Society*, 24(2), 99-117.